

Mediation Effects of Customer Trust Moderation on the Influence of Social Media Marketing and Customer Relationship Management on Online Purchase Intention in the Lazada Indonesia Marketplace

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ABSTRACT

The objective of the study is to analyze the determinant factors of online purchase intention in the marketplace in Indonesia. The factors causing the low intention to purchase online purchases include social media marketing (SMM), customer relationship management (CRM), and customer trust. In this study, the target population is the public in general who follow Lazada Indonesia's official marketplace accounts (Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, and Tiktok) through the influence of SMM and CRM on online purchase intention with mediating and moderating effects of customer trust. In this study, researchers took a sample of 18 (number of indicators) x 10 = 180 respondents. Of the 5 direct hypotheses tested, all of them showed a significant effect, except for one hypothesis, namely the influence of CRM on Purchase Intention which has no significant effect. As for the indirect effect of the two tested hypotheses, both of them showed significant results. In other words, customer trust can act as a mediator between endogenous and exogenous variables.

INTRODUCTION

Background

The number of internet users in Indonesia continues to grow significantly. This shows that Indonesia is a very attractive market for e-commerce businesses. In the last 5 years, the number of internet users has grown to 68.67 billion. The high increase in internet users in Indonesia is evidence of the high level of digital transformation in Indonesia in the development of digitalization with the potential to encourage economic growth. In addition, Indonesians also spend a relatively long time using the internet. The average time spent by Indonesians in 2021 using the internet is 8.52 hours per day, 3.14 hours of which are used for social media and the rest for Video Streaming, Music Streaming, Gaming, and Listening to Podcasts. Thus it can be understood that the lifestyle of the Indonesian people has changed and most of their time is used surfing the internet. As said by Blasco-lopez et al. (2018) that the internet has become the background for changes in the patterns and lifestyles of each individual throughout the world. Therefore, this internet-based lifestyle can provide a very promising opportunity and enable marketers to carry out online-based marketing strategies.

Since the Covid-19 pandemic, people also tend to limit their interactions with other people. The effects of this pandemic have made increase online purchases by a very significant amount compared to before the Covid-19 era. Most Indonesians have started looking for e-commerce platforms and started spending money online to meet their needs during the pandemic. Some of the marketplaces that are often used by the Indonesian people to make online purchases include Tokopedia, Shopee, Bukalapak, Lazada, and Blibli.

From the available data, the Lazada marketplace has the highest number of online followers compared to other marketplace platforms in Indonesia. However, the percentage of Lazada's monthly web visitors has the lowest percentage compared to the other 4 largest marketplaces in Indonesia. Lazada only has a visitor ratio of 7.910%, compared to competitors such as Shopee which has a ratio of 128.448%, and Bukalapak with a ratio of 67.377%. Supposedly, social media platforms with a high number of followers can lead them to visit the Lazada web marketplace every month like other marketplaces. From this data, it can be concluded that other marketplaces show the success of the SMM strategy carried out by the company in bringing visitors to visit the

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web. continue to strengthen its position in the local market or marketplace industry in the country. Meanwhile, Lazada is only in the top 4 positions under Tokopedia, Shopee and Bukalapak. From this fact, it can be seen that access to Lazada is relatively smaller than other market places such as Shopee for example. So we can say there is a phenomenon associated with repeat purchases. This is inseparable from the two types of purchases involved in sales, namely from new customers and repeats customers in the form of repeat purchases.

One of the reasons for the low return on e-marketplaces like Lazada is the lack of customer trust. Dastane (2020) said that one way to overcome consumers who are increasingly doubting digital marketing is that companies need to build customer trust, and brand trust and build a strong brand as a solution to increase consumer purchase intentions. (Dastane, 2020). Customer trust itself is defined as the customer's belief and perception of the fulfillment of organizational promises made in the delivery of services and products (Hassan & Basit, 2020). Increasing the level of customer trust perceived by consumers about products or services marketed through SMM by marketers will increase consumer intentions to buy and even make sustainable purchases. (Dastane, 2020; Hassan & Basit, 2020; Manzoor et al., 2020).

In addition to building customer trust, other causes can come from the less than optimal CRM strategy carried out by the company in serving consumers. CRM is a widely applied strategy for managing and maintaining a company's interactions with customers, clients, and sales prospects (Zamil, 2014). Zamil added strategy such as CRM involve the use of technology to organize, automate, and synchronize business processes, particularly sales, marketing, customer service, and technical support activities... The CRM concept combines the customer experience with fast and sophisticated technology changes to increase consumers' purchasing power (Putney & Puney, 2013). CRM implementation also provides more data, so consumers can understand and access strategic marketing information conveniently, and help reduce the cost of wrong marketing strategies (Stueart & Moran, 2007). Nykamp (2001) added that the application of the CRM method in digital marketing in communication, advertising, and consumer service keeps consumers loyal and satisfied with the company's products promoted on the internet.

Uniquely, not only shopping, but consumers also use social media to update their knowledge about brands and products (Casaló et al., 2017, 2018). One of the most widely used social media by users today is Instagram with the number of active users reaching one billion people. (Belanche et al., 2020). Instagram is in great demand by social media users because Instagram has a feature that can share photos and videos with various filter options that can edit user posts to make them look more attractive. (Casaló et al., 2017).

Therefore, Instagram is widely used by brands and companies to promote their products and services through influencers. Nearly nine out of ten marketers prefer to use Instagram as a medium to do their SMM (Belanche et al., 2020).

This research has a uniqueness that makes it different from previous research and has never been done before. Where in previous research, Manzoor et al. (2020) only examines the mediating effect of customer trust on the effect of marketing using social media in general on consumers' online purchase intention. This research focuses on the Lazada marketplace that implements an SMM strategy on Instagram. Other studies also only focus on the effect of digital marketing on online purchase intention with the addition of the CRM mediating variable. The study of SMM itself is a very broad study of digital marketing (Atshaya & Rungta, 2016). So in this study, the researchers narrowed the SMM variable to a more specific marketing study area, namely the SMM variable. This study also adds and combines the effects of the moderating variable of customer trust with CRM simultaneously and simultaneously which has never been done before.

The problem.

The problem in this study is the low intention to purchase at Lazada Market Place, although on the other hand, the number of followers on social media is recorded at the highest compared to other market places. This is confirmed by the ratio of followers and web visits which is relatively small compared to its competitors.

Research purposes

The purpose of this study is to find the cause of the problem by analyzing the determinant factors of intention to purchase in this online shopping industry, including social media marketing, customer relationship management, and customer trust.

REVIEW OF THEORY AND HYPOTHESES

Social Media Marketing (SMM)

Online marketing is the latest marketing tool that is used for the communication of services and products without time, location, and cost restrictions (Kim & Ko, 2012). Companies that use the SMM strategy to market their business can influence one's thinking and also influence the thinking of others more broadly before making a purchase decision (Gunelius, 2010). Wibisurya (2018) in his research also finds that digital marketing has a positive impact on purchase intention, with a large influence on attractive content, personalization, and customization for consumers. The same finding was also found by Poturak & Softić (2019) who found a positive effect of SMM on consumer purchase intentions through the exchange of opinions between consumers. Santoso & Junaedi (2021) also say that marketing activities using social media have a positive and significant

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influence on purchase intentions. In addition, Dastane (2020) also found a significant positive effect between digital-based marketing strategies and customer purchase intentions studied in several e-commerce sites in Malaysia. Social media-based communication channels play an important role in providing opportunities for every organization to carry out online-based marketing strategies (Manzoor et al., 2020).

Earlier studies said that the consistency of customer reviews and the quantity of information influence consumer purchasing decisions by increasing consumer trust (Lien et al., 2015). Manzoor et al. (2020) also found a significant positive effect between SMM and customer trust. Therefore, the hypothesis can be concluded as follows:

H1: SMM affects online purchase intention.

H2: SMM affects customer trust.

Customer Relationship Management (CRM)

Several previous studies have found that implementing a good CRM strategy in a company can increase customer repurchase intentions. A study by Ahmed & Zahid (2014) claims that a good CRM implementation has a significant impact on purchase intention. Dastane (2020) also found a significant positive effect of the CRM variable on the repurchase intention of customers who make online purchases through several e-commerce sites in Malaysia. Intayos et al. (2021) in their research said that CRM can influence purchase intention better if managers design strategies that combine behavioral control and subjective norms of customers. Another study also examined the mediating role of CRM on the effect of service evaluation (service quality, customer satisfaction, and customer value) on customer loyalty, finding that CRM strategy has a significant effect on determining customer loyalty (Nyadzayo & Khajehzadeh, 2016). That is, if customer loyalty is high then of course the customer's intention to make repeat purchases is higher. Therefore, the hypothesis can be concluded as follows:

Choi (2020) conducted a survey focusing on how cross-channel integration improves customer trust and retention. Therefore, another way to understand cross-channel integration is to propose the concept of channel integration quality. This study develops a model that explores the channel integration quality subfactors and the role of trust in customer retention in omnichannel services. To this end, the study surveyed 352 consumers using omnichannel services in South Korea and used AMOS 24 to analyze the data. As a result, first of all, content consistency and process consistency as subfactors of quality channel integration increase confidence. Second, trust enhances customer loyalty. Aslam, et al. (2020). Finally, content consistency and process consistency enhance customer loyalty through trust. Therefore, the hypothesis can be concluded as follows:

H3: CRM affects online purchase intention

H4: CRM affects customer trust

Customer Trust

Customer trust has a significant impact on customer retention variables and consumer online buying behavior (Choi, 2020). Customer confidence in online and web products has a significant impact on consumers' buying intent (Pappas, 2016). One of the most important variables in assessing a strong consumer buying intent in an online and social media buying environment is customer trust (Lu et al., 2016). Customer trust is generally defined in marketing as a consumer's willingness to repurchase a brand (Ramanathan et al., 2017). Customer trust is an important determinant of online sales variables and a functional predictor of purchase intent in electronic transactions (Wang & Chang, 2013). According to Lim (2015), trust has two directions. One direction is belief and the other is intention (Lim, 2015). Customer trust is a positive expectation and aspiration for a purchase (Chinomona & Omoruyi, 2015). Consumers recognize social media as more reliable in terms of advertising than traditional marketing elements (Schivinski & Dabrowski, 2016). This may be because social media provides direct connectivity, immediate feedback, and more specific content created for consumers (Manzoor et al., 2020). .. Pappas (2016) states that customer trust in online transactions affects online shoppers, and customer trust also motivates consumers to buy online (Hajli et al., 2017). (Manzoor et al., 2020). Therefore, the hypothesis can be concluded as follows:

H5: customer trust significantly positive effect on online purchase intention

Purchase Intention

C Beneke et al. (2013) and Faryabi et al. (2015) define the intent of online purchases as the consumer's willingness to buy a particular product. According to (Farah, 2017), intent indicates the subjective possibility that a particular action will be performed in the future. Hadlial. (2017) found that consumers' buying intentions show predictable behavior. That is, you can use your buying intent to predict what your customers will buy the next time they shop (Syahputra, A., Yunus, M., & Ibrahim, M. (Syahputra, A., Yunus, M.), & Ibrahim, M. (Syahputra, A., Yunus, M., & Ibrahim, M. (2017)). Why Consumers Buy Brands (Shah et al., 2012). Miraby et al. (2015) Define purchasing intent as a situation in which consumers tend to buy products under certain conditions.

Research Model

This research model describes the influence of the independent variable, in this case, SMM (X), and the dependent variable online purchase intention (Y), the mediating variable with moderating variables are customer trust (Z1) and CRM (Z2). Where from the flow chart of the research model below, this study wants to see the moderating

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effect of customer trust and CRM on the influence of SMM on consumers' online purchase intention in the Lazada Indonesia marketplace

Figure 1. Research Model

RESEARCH METHODS

Research Instruments

The measurement items were taken from various previous studies. Five items for measurement of purchase intention were adopted from Schiffman & Kanuk, (2007). Measurement of the SMM variable uses 5 indicators taken from Yadav & Rahman (2017). Then the CRM variable was measured using 4 items adapted from Filip (2013) and Lubis et al. (2020). Meanwhile, Customer Trust which is measured using 4 items is taken from Manzoor et al. (2020). A questionnaire with 5-point Likert scale was used to collect data.

Sample Design and Data Collection

In this study, the target population is the general public who follow Lazada Indonesia's official marketplace

accounts (Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, and Tiktok) through the influence of SMM and CRM(CRM) on online purchase intention with mediating and moderating effects of customer trust. . According to Hair (2010) which says that the number of samples can be a multiplication of the number of indicators and numbers between 5-10. In this study, researchers took a sample of 18 (number of indicators) x 10 = 180 respondents. Data were collected by using questionnaires.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characteristics of Respondents

The following information presents data on the profiles of respondents involved in this study, viewed from several aspects such as sex, occupation, and education.

Table 1. Characteristics of Respondents

No.	Description	Percentage	Frequency
1.	Gender :		
	§ Man	41.1%	74
	§ Woman	58.9%	106
2.	Respondent's age:		
	< 25 years old	16.7%	30
	26 - 30 years old	51.1%	92
	31 - 35 years old	15.6%	28
	36 - 40 years old	8.9%	16
	> 40 years old	7.8%	14
3.	Marital status		
	§ Single	47.8%	86
	§ Marry	46.1%	83
	§ Widow widower	6.1%	11

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4.	last education		
	§ SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL	10.6%	19
	Academy/Diploma	13.9%	25
	§ Bachelor	67.8%	122
	§ Postgraduate	7.8%	14
5.	Profession		
	§ College student	10.6%	19
	Civil Servant	21.7%	39
	§ Self-employed	19.4%	35
	§ Private employees	19.4%	35
	§ Etc	28.9%	52
Amount		100%	180

From the aspect of Male Gender less than women, namely 41.1% compared to 58.9%. Meanwhile, from the aspect of age, the number of respondents aged 26 - 30 years is the highest, namely 51.1%, while the lowest is those aged > 40 years, only 7.8%. When viewed from the marital status of Not Married as much as 47.8%, Married 46.1% and Widow/Widower 6.1%. the majority of respondents have a bachelor's degree (67.8%). Then when viewed from the work, it is quite balanced between civil servants, entrepreneurs, and private employees.

Instrument Test Results

Testing the instrument is by testing the validity and reliability of the question items listed in the questionnaire. The approach used in testing the validity of this questionnaire item is through convergent validity to confirm the indicator's contribution to the variable (CFA) by looking at the loading factor figures of each indicator, using the AMOS SEM. If the indicator has a loading factor coefficient > 0.50 then it is said to be valid. On the other hand, if the value is less than 0.50, it is said to be invalid and must be eliminated from this research model

Figure 2. Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

Table 2. Estimated Loading Factor

			<i>Estimate</i>
x14	<---	<i>Purchase_Intention</i>	,877
x15	<---	<i>Purchase_Intention</i>	,835
x16	<---	<i>Purchase_Intention</i>	,854
x17	<---	<i>Purchase_Intention</i>	,274
x18	<---	<i>Purchase_Intention</i>	,339
x6	<---	<i>SMM</i>	,910
x7	<---	<i>SMM</i>	,669
x8	<---	<i>SMM</i>	,358
x9	<---	<i>SMM</i>	,370

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			<i>Estimate</i>
x5	<---	<i>SMM</i>	,891
x32	<---	<i>CRM</i>	,757
x33	<---	<i>CRM</i>	,716
x34	<---	<i>CRM</i>	,753
x11	<---	<i>Customers_Trust</i>	,397
x12	<---	<i>Customers_Trust</i>	,777
x13	<---	<i>Customers_Trust</i>	,852
x31	<---	<i>CRM</i>	,779
x10	<---	<i>Customers_Trust</i>	,290

From the table above, six indicators have an LF value <0.50, namely x17, x18, x8, x9, x11, and x10. Thus, these 6 indicators must be eliminated, namely:

Reliability Test

In addition to the validity of the instrument, testing is also carried out using reliability. The author uses the

Cronbach Alpha approach. The cut-off value is 0.60. If the value of the CA coefficient > 0.60 is said to be reliable. Conversely, if it is less than 0.60 then it is said (Malhotra, 2006) the variable is not reliable.

Table 3. Research Variable Reliability Using Cronbach Alpha

No	Variable	Cronbach Alpha	Items	Information
1	<i>SMM</i>	0.878	5	Reliable
2	<i>CRM</i>	0.702	4	Reliable
3	<i>Customer Trust</i>	0.706	4	Reliable
4	<i>Purchase Intention</i>	0.801	5	Reliable

Source: Primary Data 2022 (processed)

From the output of SPSS, SMM has a CA value of 0.878 or 87.8%. Then CRM has a CA value of 0.702 or 70.2%. Furthermore, Customer Trust is 0.706 or 70.6% and Purchase Intention is 0.801 or 80.1%. So it can be concluded that all the variables contained in this research model are reliable.

Hypothesis test.

Hypothesis testing on the following structural model is to test five direct hypotheses, namely the influence of SMM and CRM on Customer Trust, the effect of SMM, customer trust, and CRM on purchase intention and

Figure 3. Structural Model for Proofing Hypotheses

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Table 4. Regression Weight Structural Equation Model

<i>Dependent</i>	<i>Independent</i>	<i>Estimate</i>	SE	CR	P	Beta
<i>Customers _Trust</i>	<--- <i>SMM</i>	,270	,084	3,233	,001	,275
<i>Customers _Trust</i>	<--- CRM	,350	0.04	8,662	***	,222
<i>Purchase Intention</i>	<--- <i>SMM</i>	,349	,039	8,660	***	,428
<i>Purchase Intention</i>	<--- <i>Cust._Trust</i>	,357	,037	8,659	***	,421
<i>Purchase Intention</i>	<--- CRM	,005	,100	0.054	,957	,004

• **Effect of SMM on OPC**

Testing the effect of SMM on Purchase Intention shows a CR value of 8,660 and a probability of ***. So the influence of SMM on OPC is significant. The P-value of the influence of SMM on OPC is 0.428 so the impact of the influence of SMM on this OPC is significant at 42.8%.

• **Effect of SMM on Customer Trust**

Testing the influence of SMM on customer trust shows a CR value of 8,662 and with a probability of ***. Then the influence of SMM on customer trust is significant. The value of the influence of SMM on customer trust is 0.222 or 22.2%.

• **Effect of CRM on OPC**

Testing the influence of CRM on OPC shows a CR value of 0.054 with a probability of 0.957. It can be stated that *CRM Effect* against OPC is not significant. The magnitude of the coefficient of CRM influence on OPC is 0.004 or only 4%. This insignificant effect could be because the impact of CRM on increased buying interest is decreasing. After all, the current trend is the increasing customer engagement of SMM which can also customize various

marketing programs carried out. This finding gives a signal to marketers to start integrating their CRM programs with social media so that the scope of CRM can be expanded without having to make additional investments for providing their servers, but using buyer profiles from IG, FB, or Twitter databases only.

• **The Effect of CRM on Customer Trust**

Testing the impact of CRM on customer trust shows a CR value of 8,662 and with a probability of ***. So the influence of CRM on customer trust is significant. The magnitude of the coefficient of CRM influence on customer trust is 0.222 or 22.2%.

• **The influence of Customer Trust on OPC in the Lazada Indonesia marketplace**

Testing the influence of customer trust on OPC shows a CR value of 8,569 and with a probability of ***. Thus the influence of customer trust on OPC is significant. The magnitude of the coefficient of influence of customer trust on OPC is .421 or 42.1%, a very large coefficient number and the largest in this structural model, so it will have a very significant impact on increasing OPC.

The Role of Customer Trust in Mediating the Effect of SMM on OPC

Figure 4. Mediation of the influence of SMM on OPC

The outcomes of testing customer trust in mediating the influence of SMM on OPC on the Lazada Indonesia marketplace have a bootstrapping p-value score of 0.006. Thus, the role of customer trust in mediating the influence of SMM on OPC in the Lazada Indonesia marketplace is

significant. Since the direct influence of SMM on OPC is significant and the indirect effect through customer trust is also significant, we can say that the role of customer trust in mediating these two variables is Partial Mediating.

The Role of Customer Trust in Mediating the Effect of CRM on OPC

Figure 5. Mediation of CRM's Effect on OPC

The outcomes of testing customer trust in mediating the influence of CRM on OPC have a p-value score of 0.001. Thus, the role of customer trust in mediating the influence of CRM on OPC is significant. The magnitude of the coefficient of the customer trust in mediating the influence of CRM on OPC is 0.094 or 9.4%. Because the direct influence of CRM on OPC is not significant and the indirect effect of CRM on OPC through customer trust is significant, we can say that the role of customer trust in mediating the influence of these two variables is full mediating.

Of the 5 hypotheses of direct influence tested, namely the influence of SMM on OPC in the Lazada Indonesia marketplace, the influence of SMM on customer trust in the Lazada Indonesia marketplace, the influence of CRM on OPC on the Lazada Indonesia marketplace, and the influence of CRM on customer trust in the Lazada Indonesia marketplace, and the influence of customer trust against OPC in the Lazada Indonesia marketplace. If it is seen which variable has the greatest dominance in moving customers to repurchase, then SMM turns out to have the highest coefficient of influence compared to other variables, namely 0.428. After that, below it, there is a customer trust variable of 0.421. Whereas the effect of SMM is not significant, even its magnitude is only 4%.

Meanwhile, for indirect influence, customer trust acts as a partial mediating to influence SMM on purchase intention, and on the influence of SMM on purchase intention, its role has actually increased to become fully mediating. On the other hand, testing the role of customer trust as a moderating variable does not meet the requirements for receiving CR and P values. So customer trust has not been able to moderate the influence of SMM on OPC. It is hoped that with the results of this research Lazada will not only be able to attract as many followers as possible on its social media but also can increase the benefits of implementing SMM and continue with changing visitor behavior to become buyers. This strategy can be

done through the latest trend at this time the use of live streaming in making sales. Many advantages are obtained by buyers and sellers in using this live streaming. Buyers can see and feel the benefits of the product because the seller demonstrates it in front of the buyer so that the buyer feels he visited the store offline. This phenomenon is shown by TikTok Live Streaming, which has also begun to be followed by Shopee but has not been followed by Lazada.

The use of live streaming TikTok other than in China is now gaining popularity in the UK and Indonesia. Recent data shows that there are more logins to TikTok than Google. So many marketers are starting to use live streaming as a medium for marketing their products. Lazada must think about this if you don't want to be left behind by direct competitors such as Shopee or indirect competitors such as TikTok and other online business platforms.

CONCLUSION

If it is seen which variable has the greatest dominance in moving customers to repurchase, then it turns out that SMM has the highest coefficient of influence compared to other variables, namely 0.428. After that, below it, there is a customer trust variable of 0.421. Meanwhile, the impact of CRM is not significant, even though its magnitude is only 4%. Thus management has very useful information in supporting the increase in purchase intention by paying full attention to the CRM which has the highest coefficient number compared to other variables.

Meanwhile, for indirect influence, customer trust acts as a partial mediating on the influence of SMM on purchase intention, and on the influence of SMM on purchase intention, its role has increased to become fully mediating. From this information, it can be seen that the two indirect effects of the significant role that can be carried out by customer trust are in the second indirect hypothesis which places customer trust as full mediating.

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